

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B360
 Date: 24 April 2008
 Take Off: 08:34:30Z
 Landing: 10:49:19Z
 Flight Time 2h 15

Campaign: ACAS

Operating Area: Rotterdam – East Anglia

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Trainer 1	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM
9	Trainer 2	Steve Devereau	FAAM
10	CVI	Paul Barrett	Met Office
11	ACAS Training	Andreas Weigelt	Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research
12	ACAS Training	Emil Carstea	INOE2000
13	ACAS Training	Sabrina Melchionna	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology
14	ACAS Training	Alberto Cazorla	Universidad de Granada
15	ACAS Training	Dina Santos	Évora Geophysics Centre
16	ACAS Training	Emilie Serf	EUFAR Office Météo-France
17	ACAS Training	Jerome Rangognio	METEO-France

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B360
 Date: 24 April 2008
 Project: ACAS
 Location: Rotterdam / East Anglia

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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075450		Start-Up	-.24 kft	000	51'56.98N, 4'26.13E
082948		ASP	-.25 kft	057	Open
083430		T/O	2.1 kft	294	Rotterdam
084106	084157	Profile 1	2.8 - 2.3 kft	307	3k'-2.5k',500fpm, QNH 1021hPa
084157	085159	Run 1	2.3 kft	302	2.5k'
084235		Event	2.3 kft	300	Zero Nevzorov & JW
085159	085315	Profile 2	2.3 - 1.3 kft	300	2.5k'-1.5k'
085315	090318	Run 2	1.3 kft	293	1.5k''
090318	090615	Profile 3	1.3 - -.12 kft	301	1.5k'-50',1kfp, QNH 1019hPa
090628	091630	Run 3	-.08 - 0.02 kft	301	100'
091352		Event	-.01 kft	275	Heimann Cal
091630	092033	Profile 4	0.02 - 4.8 kft	270	100'-5k'
092205	093144	Run 4	4.9 - 4.8 kft	090	5k'
093051		Video	4.8 kft	118	Change Tapes
093732	094446	Run 5	10.0 - 11.0 kft	260	In tops of cloud
ud					
093809		Event	10.0 kft	262	Climb to get above
093850		Event	11.1 kft	263	Above now? No, back in cloud
094705	095346	Run 6	14.0 kft	090	Above Cloud
095700	100601	Run 7	7.0 kft	247	500' above cloud base
100825	101313	Run 8	5.0 kft	086	500' below Cloud base
102044	102101	Orbit 1	19.0 kft	227	60 degrees right turn
102201		Sonde	19.1 kft	353	Launch #01
104919		Land	-.24 kft	222	Rotterdam
105259		Shutdown	-.24 kft	326	51'56.98N, 4'26.15 E

B360 Track 24-APR-08

Sortie Brief – ACAS Summer School; De Bilt, 21-24 April 2008

Flight B 360

Date: Thursday 24th April 2008

Mission Scientist: Dave Kindred

Briefing: 0520 z (0720 LT)

Take off: 0830 z (1030 LT)

Land: 1050 z (1250 LT)

Aim:

Aerosol and Trace gases variability within the PBL

Aerosol cloud interaction and cloud aging

Location:

South North Sea (Area D)

Weather conditions:

Frontal system

Key Instruments:

- all aerosol and cloud particle counters

- PSAP/Nephelometer

- CVI - aerosol mode out of cloud.

- CVI mode when in cloud

- JW, Nevzorov – ensure zero calibration when flying level in cloud – free air

Sortie Details:

Total Time (min)

Take off at Rotterdam

1. Fly for 10 min at 2500 ft	10
2. Fly for 10 min level at 1500 ft	20
3. Descent to 50 ft followed by run at 100 ft	35
4. Profile at 1000ft/min	40
5. Fly for 10 min at 5000 ft	50

→ flight direction for 1-5: perpendicular to wind direction

6. Look for low/medium level clouds:

do vertical profiling at three altitudes (10 minutes each):

- close below cloud base

- 500 ft above cloud base

- 500 ft below cloud top

90

7. Climb to 30000 ft

100

8. Dropsonde

115

9. Fly back to Rotterdam and landing

145

MISSION SCIENTIST DEBRIEFING SHEET

Date: Thursday 24th April 2008

Flight Number: B360

Overall, a successful sortie providing a variety of meteorological conditions (which were much as forecast) and two main research areas: firstly, measuring aerosol/plumes from S.England sources perpendicular to the mean low-level flow across the southern N.Sea and off the N. Norfolk coast; and secondly, ‘working’ a water-cloud layer of Sc/Ac, with S&L runs above, in and below this cloud. Instrumentation worked well, with few problems – SID 2 was unreliable (SID 1 worked OK), and less than usual warm-up time for the core instrumentation pre-take off (although no problems with core data subsequently).

The first section of the flight (sortie brief steps 1-5) were flown exactly as planned, with a general track of 300 deg from Rotterdam towards the N. coast of E.Anglia, then westwards towards the Wash, being very much perpendicular to the mean low-level boundary layer flow of 210 deg, becoming 180 – 190 deg further west.

Next, we climbed and tried to select a suitable low/medium water cloud layer to examine. Although a good Sc/Ac layer was found in the operating area, in reality it proved rather difficult to fly the required S&L legs above, in and below this cloud layer. With some ‘trial and error’, and some rapid decision-making changes and updates, we managed to make the best out of this cloud situation with runs (each of an average of around 7 minutes) at:

- (a) FL100, then FL 110 (run near cloud-top)
- (b) FL140 (run above cloud top)
- (c) FL 070 (run near cloud base) &
- (d) FL 050 (run under cloud base).

[See Fig 1, attached, for sketch of cloud & runs made, and more details.]

Thereafter, we climbed to FL190 and then:

- (a) Performed a 2g, 60 deg bank-angle orbit (rolling to the right) through about 270 deg, for radiometer calibrations.
- (b) Dropped a sonde, which worked well, giving good met and wind data all the way down to the surface.

Finally, we recovered to Rotterdam, landing at 1049z, after a 2h 14 min flight duration.

Weather conditions: Visibility was generally good over the southern N.Sea, deteriorating somewhat as we neared the approaching frontal surface whilst operating over and to the N of E.Anglia. Cloud increased with time, and also the further west we headed. Some haze and low stratus was present over the Rotterdam area initially, soon dispersing. Ci/Cs cloud increased from small amounts near the Dutch coast, to 8/8 cover near the Wash area. Layers of low and medium frontal cloud increased in thickness, again as we neared the front, and with time. Winds were generally S – SSW, light to moderate at low level, increasing slowly with height.

Overall, a very good final Education & Training sortie, with many planning, logistical and flying-related problems overcome and with some good lessons learnt. This flight should provide a wealth of core and cloud physics data for useful analysis by the students. Good Luck !

DRK
25/04/08

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B360** Date **24/4/08** Name **DRK [initials]** Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0827.			→		START TAXI . T/O FROM RUNWAY 24.
					Passed the Falconer (bird scarer) on taxi.
0835					T/O ROTTERDAM
					v. hazy.
0835			→		Into 8T at ~900'
					8T tops ~1800'. Generally clear above Some Ci (thin) ahead
0835		3000'	→		Now just off Dutch coast
					Wx conditions better than expected.
					Good vis, v. little cloud ahead (W) just 1/8 - 1/8 Ci to NW.
084106	START P1	3000' ↓	300°		[QNH 2102 mb]
084157	END P1 / START R1	2500'	300°		Start R1 at 2500', heading WNW.
0843			→		Wind 210/15 kT (EXERCISE HOR to BL. wind) OAT +7.3°C.
084930			→		5/8 Ci / Contrails above & to N/NE Some thin Sc layer (+ some Cu) to Port (1/8) (i.e. to SW)
0850			→		v. little seen on PCASP (4200h) high O3/CO values near Rotterdam less now over southern N! Sea.
085159	END R1 / P2 START	2500'	300°		End R1 / Start P2 ↓ 2500' + 1500' @ 500'/min
					Logr. Equip ahead, will try aftly behind it's plane (for any pollution)
085315	END P2 / START R2	1500'	293°		→ alt change in bearing for ↑ [CWI: CO Mixing ratio ↑ (BOT IN CAL MODE !!)]
0857			→		CiCs deck now covering forward horizon Passing under Sc/CO deck above (3/8) Generally thickening Med/cloud well ahead.
090318	END R2 / START P3	1500' ↓	301°	5242m 2°6'W	Descent to 500ft. (500'/min).
090630	END P3	50'	302°		At 50', climb to 100'
090628	R3	100'	295°		Start R3 at 100' wind 180/10kt. [1019 mb]

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B360** Date **24/4/08** Name **DEK** Page **2** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
091030	R3	100'			Now passing close to N. Norfolk Coast. More mechanical turbulence here! (downwind of land).
091130	R3	100'			
					3/8 Cs above & ahead Low level cloud layers ahead to SW 1/8 Small Cu ahead
					100' Wind 15 180-200 S present track still almost 1 hr to this
091630	END R3 START P4	100'	272°		END R3, START P4 ↑ 5000' @ 100'/min
092030	P4	5000'	274°		END P4 at 5000' returning ↓ back into EAST.
092205	START R4	5000'	091°		START R4, tracking East (AIR TRAFFIC RESTRICTIONS) (last pollution part of sortie)
0930					1/8 Cu below
093144	END R4	5000'			Turn ↓ onto N South & ↑ climb to FL100 to view medium level layer cloud
	* END	SORTIE BEIER # 5 ; onto C. PHYSICS PART X. ↓			
	Now	looking for suitable (water) layer cloud. (seems to be gone to SW, top ~ 5000-6000' ??) base ~ 6000'			
093732	START R5	FL100			Climbs to try & get above cloud top? (ascend to FL110)
093850	START R5	FL110	NW		IN EAST OF CLOUD "600' below cloud top" (A)
094440	END R5	FL110			CASE THIS "REW" Ascend to be (B)
094705	START R6	FL140	NE		ABOVE cloud top. (EXTRA) (B) Next descend to FL070 (above cloud base)?
095346	END R6	FL140			END R6
095700	R7	FL070	NW		START R7 Start in clear air, will go into cloud along run.
0958					(CO CAL) * In cloud (500 above C BASE) RW * (C)
1000					Into cloud (seen on cloud P, 2 DC/ADC) 700 min on 2X
100230					CVI - increasing values

(SEE FIG 1 ATTACHED)

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B360** Date **24/4/08** Name **DLK** Page **3** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
100601	END R7	FLO70	247°	-	END R7 Turn & descend to try & be below cloud base.
	Next run				will be at FLO50. (Maybe in cloud at start of run). RUN W/UNDER C. BASE.
100825	START R8	FLO50	086°		now just under main cloud base.
100920					w/ slightly thicker cloud now.
100940					Now under main base; underneath
101040					[too 2DP 200 on 2DC C-Physics]
101313	END R8	FLO50			[in cloud early part of run - C. BASE USING X-RAYS THIS RUN] Climb to FL190 for orbit & send drop & RTB.
101530					Passing thru higher cloud layer now
101730		Rising FL155			Orbit will be \approx [60°] (2g).
101805		FL 166			7/8 C1/Cs above ahead (to E). 1/8 Cw/Sc layer below.
		Prepare for			RAH orbit (Radiometer cal ^s) (FL190)
102014		Rolling into			60° turn.
102104		Rolling out			of 60° orbit. (After about 270° of orbit).
102204	SEND DROP	FL190	NN		Drop side #1 released (off Norfolk coast) Good met & good wind data.
INSTRUMENT STATUS CHECK:					FLIGHT MANAGER
		⊙ CWI -			Worked well! (good run in cloud)
		⊙ C. Physics -			PCASP ✓ [5152?] ALL ELSE WORKED FINE ✓
		⊙ CORE atom.			✓ ok
		⊙ DDP/SENDE			✓ ok
103450	Descent into Rotterdam	13260'	132°		6/8 Cw/Sc below. 7/8 C1/Cs above ahead.
1049					LAND ROTTERDAM (R/W 024)

0835

2hr 14min

Runs 5, 6, 7, 8 between about 5 mins & 9 mins

FIG ① — SEE AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST LOG
PP 2/3 & A/SC DE-BRIEFING SHEET.

B360 24/4/08.

JKK

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 24/04/08	Operator: pdr	DRS Time: 0	DAU1 Time: 0	DAU2 Time: 0	DAU3 Time: 0	Aux1 Time: 0	Aux2 Time: 0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
				SID 2 voltage very low													
8:41:00	400	0.09	74														Profile1
8:42:00	377	0.09	74	10	10												Start run 1 fl23
8:46:00	320	0.09	74	10	10												
8:48:00	230	0.08	75	10	10												
8:50:00	100	0.09	75	1	1												
8:52:00	100	0.09	75	1	1												End run2 start profile2
8:53:14	137	0.09	75	3	3												End profile2 start run3 fl13
8:56:00	100	0.09	75	1	1												
8:58:00	200	0.08	75	1	1												
09:00:30	100	0.09	75	1	1												
09:02:00	90	0.09	75	1	1												
09:03:18	400	0.09	75	10	10												End run2 start profile3
09:06:15	2200	0.09	75	50	50												End profile 3 at 50ft start run 3 at 100ft
09:08:00	1000	0.09	76	10	10												
09:10:00	850	0.07	76	10	10												
09:12:00	970	0.09	76	20	10												
09:14:00	470	0.09	76	10	10												
09:16:00	500	0.09	77	10	10												End run 3 start profile 4
9:19:20	100	0.09	78	10	10												Fl 30
09:20:32	100	0.09	78	10	10												End profile4
09:22:05	183	0.11	78	10	10												Start run4
09:24:00	100	0.1	78	10	10												
09:30:00	125	0.09	78	1	0												
09:31:43	130	0.09	78	1	0												End run 4
09:37:32	130	0.1	79	1	10												Start run5 above cloud FL110
09:40:00	78	0.12	115	1	100												Bits of cloud in this run
09:43:00	50	0.14	117	10	1000	8	600	500	0							4	
09:44:46	148	0.11	181	1000	1000	1	0	150	0							4	End run5
09:47:06	75	0.1	330	1	200	0		0									Start run6 above cloudFL140
09:49:00	140	0.1	220	0	100												
09:51:00	130	0.09	220	1	10												

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.6	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.6	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = 1	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =0.82		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =0.7	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =34	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =3	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
			CIP100 End element 64 voltage =

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B360 **T/O:** 083430
Date of flight: 24/04/08 **Land:** 104919

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = 8,9,10 Last sec processed = 105649
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size = fine
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B360
Date of Flight: 24/04/08

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		y
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip		Size of Bnnn.dat = 104038
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read =23971 Blocks written = 23971 Bad reads =0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y Y Y Y Y N n	Start =0 End = 240000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size? Yes
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images No problems Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 0 End =240000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =3680</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p> <p>okay</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size =0 Vol flow rate = 0.8 0 240000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check. okay

b360_cvi_log & b360_cvi_log2

4/24/08 8:51:54 AM no horace feed, will perform a restart

4/24/08 8:52:56 AM horace feed ok, pcasp ok, cpc ok

4/24/08 8:53:04 AM startup lyman alpha

4/24/08 8:53:31 AM zero lyman,

4/24/08 8:53:38 AM counterflow is on

4/24/08 8:54:00 AM opc sample flow reduced

4/24/08 8:57:55 AM another lyman zero

4/24/08 8:58:13 AM will now reconnect lyman to sample flow

4/24/08 9:08:42 AM counterflow will be on until just prior to takeoff

4/24/08 9:08:50 AM ccn to turn counterflow off.

4/24/08 9:09:06 AM CVI will operate in aerosol mode for the transit and low level work

4/24/08 10:20:52 AM CVI will operate in aerosol mode for the transit and low level work

4/24/08 10:21:16 AM rub4 below sc layer, in aerosol mode

4/24/08 10:32:06 AM

4/24/08 10:32:23 AM attempt zero cloud mode

4/24/08 10:32:29 AM pressure pump on

4/24/08 10:32:35 AM l= 2.2

4/24/08 10:35:33 AM straight and level now, counts are very low with counterflow on,

4/24/08 10:35:44 AM will use this L value for the in cloud run

4/24/08 10:36:34 AM start of run just switched off pressure pump

4/24/08 10:37:12 AM climb to get above cloud

4/24/08 10:37:38 AM run start

4/24/08 10:37:47 AM cloud tops, varying altitude

4/24/08 10:39:25 AM back in cloud, still in aerosol mode

4/24/08 10:39:47 AM 'look - see' run, to assess the cloud layer

4/24/08 10:40:53 AM 'look - see' run, to assess the cloud layer

4/24/08 10:41:00 AM 'look - see' run, to assess the cloud layer

4/24/08 10:41:09 AM 'look - see' run, to assess the cloud layer

4/24/08 10:41:13 AM 'look - see' run, to assess the cloud layer

4/24/08 10:46:18 AM run out of cloud

4/24/08 10:47:23 AM This run is above cloud

4/24/08 10:47:30 AM next run will be the in cloud run

4/24/08 10:52:44 AM run end

4/24/08 10:53:35 AM pressure pump on

4/24/08 10:55:57 AM run start

4/24/08 10:58:49 AM run start

4/24/08 10:59:26 AM run start

4/24/08 10:59:30 AM run start

4/24/08 11:00:40 AM run start

4/24/08 11:00:45 AM run start

4/24/08 11:00:51 AM run start

4/24/08 11:01:19 AM reduce l value

4/24/08 11:01:24 AM reduce l value

4/24/08 11:07:54 AM reduce l value

4/24/08 11:08:14 AM reduce l value

4/24/08 11:08:59 AM counterflow turned off halfway through run, as now out of cloud base

4/24/08 11:21:57 AM end of science

4/24/08 11:22:16 AM leave in aerosol mode to sample pollution into rotterdam

4/24/08 11:25:51 AM zero lyman

4/24/08 11:27:38 AM dried cabin air is more moist than ambient!

4/24/08 11:27:50 AM will not zero

4/24/08 11:29:43 AM pressure pump off#

4/24/08 11:53:00 AM landed, turn off

Flight:

B360

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B360

Date: 24 April 2008

Instruments

1. Pre-flight – very short!!! Only 40 minutes before take-off . Core chem. instruments likely to be affected.
2. Video – On laptop, can't access RFC pre-flight. Reconnected cables to video box then okay.

Status roundup

CVI – Worked well

Cloud Physics – 2D-P and 2D-C as yesterday

Core chem. –no problems

Dropsonde – good data

Aircraft

Nil

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

1 from DFL to aircraft

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 24/04/08

Flight No: B 360

Pre-Flighter: MS, scd, PDR, DHA

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input type="checkbox"/>			
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	<i>Not fitted</i>
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
External Checks				
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	<i>No photo taken</i>
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36	<input type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Avalon Checks				<u>Signed</u>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B360:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as any PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	02 May 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras

2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080424_b360_082238_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080424_b360_092238_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080424_b360_102238_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080424_b360_082217_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080424_b360_092217_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080424_b360_102217_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080424_b360_081529_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080424_b360_082213_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080424_b360_092213_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080424_b360_102213_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080424_b360_081536_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080424_b360_082221_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080424_b360_092221_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080424_b360_102221_1hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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